

Supplementary Material

Farming for the environment and climate: Why farmers in the German-French border region adopt agri-environmental practices

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This document complements the main article with material that supports specific claims or methodological choices, but that would have exceeded the article's length budget.

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S1. COM-C OPERATIONALISATION

S1.1 COM-C operationalisation: Capability

Capability addresses farm-level feasibility: whether the farmer-farm-unit possesses the knowledge, skills, physical resources (land, labor, capital, equipment) and remaining absorptive capacity needed to implement a practice. We extend Michie et al.'s (2011) original individual-centered conception to capture the operational unity between farmer and farm in agricultural contexts. The farm is not an external environment but an extension of the farmer's capacity to act. Its land base, labor pool, and equipment endowment function as internal resources that the farmer can, at least in principle, manage, develop, or reallocate. Absorptive capacity reflects the saturation effect identified inductively in the data. Even where motivation, knowledge and external opportunity align, a farmer who has already enrolled all compatible land and exhausted the available measure catalogue faces a ceiling on further adoption (Section 4.3.1 main text, Saturation cluster). Capability is therefore distinguished from Opportunity by a clear criterion. A constraint belongs to Capability if it could in principle be addressed by the farmer-farm-unit acting differently, for example by reallocating labor, acquiring equipment, or learning new practices. It belongs to Opportunity if it is fixed from the farmer's perspective.

S1.2 COM-C operationalisation: Opportunity

Opportunity is defined, following Michie et al. (2011), as all factors that lie outside the individual that make the behavior possible or prompt it. We operationalize it at the AES and local level, capturing three sub-dimensions. (i) Policy-created conditions, such as payment adequacy, administrative burden, AES flexibility, technical assistance, and monitoring requirements. (ii) The immediate social environment that shapes adoption, such as peer influence, advisory networks, cooperative expectations, and local community dynamics. (iii) The biophysical and structural feasibility of the practice itself, such as weather, disease, market or coordination constraints that any farmer attempting the practice would face, independent of their specific farm endowment. Sub-dimensions (i) and (iii) jointly correspond to Michie et al.'s "physical opportunity". Sub-dimension (ii) corresponds to "social opportunity".

S1.3 COM-C operationalisation: Motivation

Motivation is operationalized here as in Section 3.3 of the main text. Two structural adaptations of the original COM-B (Michie et al., 2011) underpin the COM-C framework as a whole and apply to Motivation by implication. First, Capability is extended from the individual to the farmer-farm-unit, reflecting the operational inseparability of farmer and farm in agricultural production contexts. Second, Opportunity is restricted to AES-level and local-level factors, with broader systemic conditions reserved for the fourth dimension (Context). Motivation itself follows COM-B's definition.

S1.4 COM-C operationalisation: Context and framework integration

Context represents our extension from COM-B to COM-C, which emerged iteratively during data analysis. It captures structural conditions operating at the systems level that shape adoption possibilities but require complementary intervention beyond AES design. While Opportunity captures what AES designers and local actors can directly influence, Context encompasses market conditions (e.g. product prices, retail power), trade exposure and international competition, regulatory coherence across policy domains, rural infrastructure, and socio-cultural norms including societal appreciation of agriculture. These are factors that condition the effectiveness of AES-level Opportunity.

This conceptualization resonates with recent efforts to address COM-B's individualistic focus. Nguyen-Trung et al. (2025) propose a Socio-Ecological COM-B (SeCOM-B) that integrates Bronfenbrenner's nested systems (Bronfenbrenner, 1977) into the Opportunity component. While SeCOM-B embeds Opportunity within concentric ecological layers (micro-, meso-, exo-, macrosystem), our COM-C approach

conceptualises context as a distinct analytical category that captures structural constraints shaping farmer behaviour independently of, and often prior to, individual capability and motivation. This draws on practice theory (Shove et al., 2012) and the ISM framework (Darnton & Horne, 2013), which emphasize that practices are embedded in social and material structures transcending individual choice architectures. Context factors are slower-moving, require cross-sectoral coordination, and fundamentally condition whether AES-level opportunities translate into adoption.

COM-C clarifies intervention leverage points across scales and timescales. Capability interventions target the farmer-farm-unit (e.g. knowledge transfer, capital and labor support). Opportunity interventions target AES, local networks, and the structural-biophysical conditions of practices themselves (e.g. CAP redesign, administrative simplification, advisory systems, cooperative engagement, agronomic R&D). Context interventions target systems (e.g. market policy, trade agreements, cultural change), each requiring different actors and resources. The framework also distinguishes practice adoption (with or without incentives) from AES participation (enrolment in AECMs, eco-schemes, or other AES), recognizing that all four dimensions influence adoption broadly while Opportunity factors specifically shape AES participation.

Categories are analytically distinct but empirically interconnected. Context shapes Opportunity effectiveness (well-designed AES may fail if market conditions undermine farm viability, or if local social dynamics discourage participation despite adequate payments). Capability interacts with Opportunity to determine feasibility. All condition whether Motivation translates into action. Rather than forcing observations into single categories, we coded according to primary analytical function while noting cross-category relationships through dual coding where a single statement clearly addressed two analytically distinct dimensions. The framework's value lies in clarifying intervention points rather than eliminating overlap.

S2. INSTITUTIONAL AND POLICY CONTEXT: GERMANY AND FRANCE

S2.1 Institutional architecture

Germany's federal system delegates significant authority to its states (Länder). In Baden-Württemberg, agricultural governance flows through a single state hierarchy, from the ministry (MLR) through the regional councils (Regierungspräsidien) to the lower agricultural authorities (Untere Landwirtschaftsbehörden, ULBs) at district level. In Baden-Württemberg, specialized advice runs through accredited private organizations under the subsidized Beratung.Zukunft.Land scheme, which covers 70 to 85% of module costs (<https://bz.landwirtschaft-bw.de/Lde/Startseite/Beratungsmodule>).

The French system distributes governance across institutions with distinct mandates. The central state operates through the DRAAF at regional level and the DDT at departmental level, the latter managing CAP payments, agri-environmental contracts, and controls, broadly comparable to the German ULBs. The Région Grand Est is managing authority for parts of Pillar II. The agricultural chambers provide hands-on technical assistance to farmers. This assistance is largely fee-based (chambres-agriculture.fr). AECMs are territorialized through regional agri-environmental projects (PAECs), operated by chambers or nature parks, which draw up the specification sheets that set eligibility and management requirements (DRAAF Grand Est, 2024).

In France, area-based AECMs take two forms. System measures (MAEC systèmes) apply one set of requirements to at least 90 percent of the farm. Localized measures (MAEC localisées) are taken parcel by parcel for a circumscribed local stake. Our notion of whole-farm approaches is broader than the French

system measures, because it also covers organic and HVE certification and the eco-scheme practices pathway.

S2.2 The Landschaftspflegerichtlinie and the German funding architecture

In Baden-Württemberg, the principal AECM portfolio runs through FAKT II under the national CAP Strategic Plan (GAP-Strategieplan). Alongside it, the Landschaftspflegerichtlinie (LPR) is a contractual conservation programme with a split funding structure. Its Section A (Vertragsnaturschutz) is ELER-cofinanced and forms part of the CAP Strategic Plan, functionally equivalent to an AECM though administered separately from FAKT II. Sections B to F are funded from Land resources alone, outside the CAP Strategic Plan. The share of LPR-supported practices in our sample that runs through Section A rather than Sections B to F cannot be reconstructed from interview data alone. LPR-supported practices are therefore counted as AES-supported throughout this study. This layering of nature conservation policy alongside agricultural policy at the Land level has no direct counterpart in the more centrally coordinated French system. It is part of what the most-similar-systems design holds variable across the border.

S2.3 Selected references for measure catalogues

For the German eco-scheme and CAP AECM catalogue in Baden-Württemberg, see MLR (n.d., 2026). For the French eco-scheme and AECM catalogue in the Grand Est, see MAASA (2025) and DRAAF Grand Est (2023). Catalogues are revised annually, and the analysis reflects the versions in effect for the 2024 CAP application campaigns, which preceded or coincided with the interview period.

S3. SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS WITH CROSS-BORDER BREAKDOWN

S3.1 Practice categories by country, compensation, farm type and topography

Supplementary Table S3.1: Distribution of 186 agri-environmental farming systems and practices as claimed by 62 farms in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France) for 2024, with cross-border breakdown

Category	Type of agri-environmental system/practice	n	% sample (N=62)	% in DE	% in FR	% of n AES-supported	Main farm type(s)	% of n in mountain
FARMINGS SYSTEMS	Organic farming (certified)	10	16%	13%	19%	100%	Perennial (wine)	40%
	Organic farming (uncertified)	3	5%	3%	6%	0%	Grassland	100%
	High Environmental Value (cert., FR only)	9	15%	0%	29%	100%	Grassland, Mixed	11%
	Other environmental certification	2	3%	3%	3%	0%	Arable/Market	100%
	French eco-scheme (practices pathway)	6	10%	0%	19%	100%	Grassland	17%
<i>Individual parcel-based Agri-environmental Practices not covered above and not required by regulation or conditionality:</i>								
Soil & Crop Management	No use of (phyto-)sanitary measures	12	19%	29%	10%	50%	Grassland	100%
	Reduced/managed use of (phyto-)san.	17	27%	39%	16%	33%	Arable/Market	18%
	No use of synthetic fertilizers	13	21%	29%	13%	46%	Grassland	92%
	Reduced/managed use of synth. fert.	15	24%	39%	10%	53%	Arable/Market, Grassland	33%
	No tilling	4	6%	3%	10%	25%	Perennial (wine)	25%
Landscape & Habitat Management	Less frequent mowing of grassland	5	8%	6%	10%	0%	Grassland, Perennial	20%
	Establishment of trees and hedges	5	8%	0%	16%	20%	Perennial (wine)	20%
	Maintenance of trees/fruit trees	23	37%	42%	32%	30%	Grassland	70%
	Landscape conservation	14	23%	32%	13%	57%	Grassland	79%
	Hydrological landscape elements	3	5%	0%	10%	33%	Arable/Market	33%
Biodiversity conservation	Conservation of plant biodiversity	14	23%	32%	13%	79%	Arable/Market, Grassland	57%
	Conservation of animal biodiversity	9	15%	19%	10%	56%	Grassland	56%
	High Nature Value farming	5	8%	13%	3%	80%	Grassland	60%
Animals	Animal welfare measures	10	16%	32%	6%	55%	Grassland	70%
Other	Other	7	11%	0%	0%	0%	Grassland	71%

Source: Authors' development..

S3.2 Additionality and permanence: cross-tabulation by country

Supplementary Table S3.2: Subjective assessment by farms (N=62) of the additionality and permanence of financially supported agri-environmental farming systems and practices implemented for 2024 in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France), with cross-border breakdown

	Total (N=62)		Germany (n=31)		France (n=31)	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
ADDITIONALITY						
Agri-environmental farming systems	17		3		14	
Low (would certify/participate anyway)	11	65	2	67	9	64
High (would not without support)	6	35	1	33	5	36
Agri-environmental practices	30		24		6	
Low (would implement all anyway)	13	43	10	42	3	50
Partial (would implement some)	12	40	9	38	3	50
High (would not implement any without support)	5	17	5	21	0	0
PERMANENCE						
Agri-environmental farming systems	15		2		13	
Permanent integration	11	73	2	100	9	69
Would continue <2 years	3	20	0	0	3	23
Not sure	1	7	0	0	1	8
Agri-environmental practices	18		15		3	
Permanent integration	14	78	11	73	3	100
Would stop immediately	4	22	4	27	0	0
Would continue for a limited period	0	0	0	0	0	0

Note: Additionality and permanence assessments cover two ordinal scale questions: whether farmers would implement agri-environmental activities without support and what they would do with the agri-environmental activity if the contract ended today.

Source: Authors' development.

S3.3 Practice-level additionality breakdown

The practice-level breakdown qualifies the farm-level pattern reported in main text Table 5 in three ways. First, additionality varies substantially across practices. *Landscape conservation* stands out with uniformly high additionality (5 of 5 compensated respondents would not maintain the practice without subsidy), as do *no use of synthetic fertilizers* (2 of 5 with high additionality) and *reduced/managed use of synthetic fertilizers* (3 of 7). At the opposite end, *animal welfare measures* and *maintenance of (scattered fruit) trees* show predominantly low additionality, suggesting that compensation primarily recognises practices already embedded in farm routines. Second, several categories never appear with financial support: *less frequent mowing of grassland*, *establishment of trees and hedges*, and *other* measures are implemented exclusively without compensation. The structural association reported in main text Figure 4 between less frequent mowing and non-compensation ($\phi = -0.46$) is therefore not driven by a small subset of farms but holds categorically. Third, the permanence question yields too few evaluable responses per practice to support firm interpretation, but the limited data point in a consistent direction. The practices with the highest additionality are also those where farmers express the highest intent to stop if support ends. Together these patterns suggest that the modest aggregate additionality reported at the farm level (Table 5) masks a meaningful internal divide. A small set of structurally embedded practice categories drives the high-additionality signal, while the bulk of compensated practices would persist without support.

Supplementary Table S3.3: Subjective assessment by farms (N=62) of the additionality and permanence of financially supported agri-environmental farming systems and individual practices implemented in 2024 in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France), broken down by practice category

Practice category	ADDITIONALITY				PERMANENCE				
	n	Low %	Partial %	High %	n	Perm. integr. %	Stop immed. %	<2 yrs %	Not sure %
AGRI-ENVIRONMENTAL FARMING SYSTEMS:									
Practices pathway of French eco-scheme	5	60	40	0	4	50	0	50	0
Organic farming (certified)	5	80	20	0	3	100	0	0	0
High Environmental Value (HVE)	6	100	0	0	2	100	0	0	0
INDIVIDUAL AGRI-ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES not covered above and not required by regulation or conditionality:									
No use of (phyto-)sanitary measures	6	67	0	33	3	33	0	33	33
Reduced/managed use of (phyto-)sanitary measures	4	50	25	25	2	50	50	0	0
No use of synthetic fertilizers	5	60	0	40	3	67	0	33	0
Reduced/managed use of synthetic fertilizers	7	57	0	43	3	0	67	0	33
No tilling	1	100	0	0	1	0	0	0	100
Less frequent mowing of grassland	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Establishment of trees and hedges	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Maintenance of (scattered fruit) trees	5	80	0	20	1	0	0	0	100
Landscape conservation	5	0	0	100	3	33	33	0	33
Hydrological landscape elements	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Conservation of plant biodiversity	9	56	0	44	5	20	60	0	20
Conservation of animal biodiversity	4	50	0	50	2	50	50	0	0
High Nature Value farming	2	50	0	50	3	33	0	67	0
Animal welfare measures	3	100	0	0	2	100	0	0	0
Other	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Note: Cells show the share of evaluable responses falling in each category for each farming system and practice. n is the number of financially supported farm-by-practice combinations with an evaluable response.

Additionality and permanence assessments cover two ordinal scale questions: whether farmers would implement agri-environmental activities without support and what they would do with the agri-environmental activity if the contract ended today.

The two intermediate responses (3 = continue 2 to 5 years, 4 = continue more than 5 years) did not occur in the per-practice data of additionality. The denominator for permanence is consistently smaller than for additionality because the permanence question was asked of a narrower subset of respondents.

Source: Authors' development..

S3.4 Self-Determination Theory motivation and needs profile: cross-border comparison

The cross-border breakdown of motivation types and basic psychological needs shows a high degree of structural similarity between the two sub-samples, with one consistent and analytically meaningful exception. Across the autonomous end of the SDT continuum (Intrinsic, Integrated, Identified motivation), German and French farmers report nearly identical mean scores, with French values marginally higher by 0.12 to 0.18 points on the four-point scale. External motivation is essentially flat across both sub-samples (DE M = 1.81, FR M = 1.82). The two cross-border differences worth flagging are both located in the controlled-to-amotivated end of the continuum. Introjected motivation, capturing internalised pressure to act in line with social or self-imposed expectations, is substantially higher in France (M = 3.06) than in Germany (M = 2.48), the largest cross-border gap in the figure. Amotivation, capturing a disengagement from the perceived effectiveness of one's own environmental action, is also higher in France (M = 2.34) than in Germany (M = 1.76).

On the basic psychological needs, the pattern is reversed. German farmers report marginally higher satisfaction across all four need dimensions, with the gap most visible for Relatedness (Social) (DE M = 3.36, FR M = 3.16).

Supplementary Figure S3.4: Motivations for adoption of agri-environmental farming systems and individual practices and basic psychological needs satisfaction of farmers (N=62) in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France) for 2024, with cross-border breakdown for Landkreis Ortenau, Germany (n=31) and Arrondissement of Molsheim, France (n=31)

Notes: Panel (a) shows the six motivation types for the combined sample (yellow). Panel (b) shows the cross-border split (DE blue, FR red). Panel (c) shows the four need dimensions for the combined sample (yellow). Panel (d) shows the cross-border split. Source: Authors' development, adapted from (Gagné, 2003; Mayer & Frantz, 2004; Pelletier et al., 1998; Ryan & Deci, 2000)

S4. INTERVIEW GUIDE

This questionnaire was originally developed and administered in German and French. The following represents an English translation of the interview guide used for semi-structured interviews with farmers in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France).

Section 1: Farm and farmer characteristics

At the start of each interview, structured information on farm structure, farmer socio-demographics, and income was recorded. The resulting sample characteristics are summarized in Table 3 of the main text.

Section 2: Inventory of agri-environmental activities and external support

- Which agri-environmental activities did you carry out on your farm in 2024?

For each activity, the following information was recorded: area or number of animals, year(s) of implementation, establishment vs. maintenance, and whether support were received.

- Which external support do you receive (CAP direct payments, agri-environmental support, etc.)?

Verified with joint application payment notification where available.

Section 3: Understanding adoption and non-adoption

Open-ended questions exploring farmers' reasons and circumstances:

- What reasons and circumstances contribute to you establishing or maintaining agri-environmental activities on your farm, respectively?

- What reasons and circumstances contribute to you NOT establishing or NOT maintaining agri-environmental activities on your farm, respectively?

- What do you like about the current design of agri-environmental support schemes?

Explain where necessary.

- What do you dislike about the current design of agri-environmental support schemes?

Satisfaction with schemes. Response scale: 1 = Not at all satisfied, 4 = Completely satisfied.

- Are you satisfied with the design of AECMs?

- Are you satisfied with the Eco-Schemes?

Section 4: Additionality and permanence

Asked only to farmers currently receiving support:

- If the support for agri-environmental activities was not available, would you maintain or have introduced the activity/-ies on your farm?

Response options: Yes, all of them / Yes, but only some of them / No, none of the activities / Not sure.

- To what extent was the support for agri-environmental activities the main reason for maintaining or introducing the activity/-ies on your farm?

Response options: Main reason / One of several reasons / Minor role / No influence / Not sure.

- What are your intentions after your contracts expire / for next payment period?

Response options: Terminate / Re-sign for same area / Re-sign for smaller area / Re-sign for larger area / Not sure.

- If support for agri-environmental activities was discontinued today, would you continue to maintain or establish the activity/-ies on your farm?

Response options: Stop immediately / Continue for short time (<2 years) / Continue for medium time (2-5 years) / Continue long-term (>5 years) / Permanent part of farming practice / Not sure.

Section 5: Motivation for agri-environmental activities & Satisfaction of basic psychological needs

Please indicate the extent to which you agree with each item. Scale: 1 (not at all) to 4 (completely).¹

Motivation for agri-environmental activities

#	Item
1	Other people will be upset if I don't
2	A way I've chosen to contribute
3	An integral part of my life
4 (R)	Don't know; can't see what I'm getting out of it
5	For the recognition I get from others
6	Would feel guilty if I didn't
7	I'd regret not doing something
8	Is a sensible thing to do
9 (R)	I wonder why; the situation isn't improving
10	Seems that taking care of myself and environment are inseparable
11	Like feeling when doing things for environment
12	Pleasure in improving quality of environment

Satisfaction of basic psychological needs

#	Item
13	I often feel a sense of oneness with the natural world around me
14	When I decide to do something for the environment, I can implement it
15 (R)	There are not many opportunities for me to decide for myself how to do things in my daily life
16	I like the people I interact with very much
17	I feel I can pretty much be myself in my daily situations
18 (R)	My personal welfare is independent of the welfare of the natural world
19 (R)	I often do not feel very capable of implementing agri-environmental activities
20	The people in my life care about me

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¹ Items adapted from the *Motivation Toward the Environment Scale (MTES; Pelletier et al., 1998)*. (R) indicates reverse-coded items.

Items 13 and 18 are from the *Connectedness to Nature Scale (Mayer & Frantz, 2004)*. Items 14, 15, 16, 17, 19, and 20 adapted from the *Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction Scales (BPNSS) (Gagné, 2003; Ryan & Deci, 2000)*. (R) indicates reverse-coded items.

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